

Drought resistance

IR5178-1-1-4, an outstanding drought-tolerant line

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Moisture level and stress affect the performance of rice. In 1979, reduced rainfall at the RRS, Nagina U.P., lasted 88 days. The normal rainfall during the monsoon season is 800 mm, but in 1979, only 337.5 mm was recorded. Between 25 July and 20 October only 27 mm of rain fell.

During 1979 kharif, the International Upland Rice Yield Nursery (IURYN) seeds were sown on 29 June. Nagina 22 was sown as a local check. Only two varieties, IR5178-1-1-4 and Nagina 22 flowered and set seed (see photo). They produced yields of 1.43 and 0.27 t/ha, respectively (see table). The non-flowering varieties dried up.

The crop did not suffer from moisture stress during the first 26 days of the drought (29 Jun - 25 Jul); therefore, crop establishment was good. But moisture stress was acute after that period.

The performance of IR5178-1-1-4 under acute moisture stress was remarkable. The mechanism of its drought tolerance needs investigation. ■

Nagina scientists at IURYN plot. Rice breeder points out the seeded variety.

Performance of IR5178-1-1-4 and the check Nagina 22 in the IURYN. Rice Research Station, Nagina, India, 1979.

Variety	Days to heading	Days to maturity	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
IR5178-1-1-4	57	88	85.2	18.1	1.43
Nagina 22	81	109	58.1	16.4	0.27

Temperature tolerance

Thermosensitivity of aus and boro varieties of Bangladesh

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Aus and boro varieties are photoperiod-insensitive rice groups of Bangladesh. They have been cultivated for centuries under distinct ecological conditions. The

vegetative, reproductive, and ripening phases of aus varieties always experience high temperature but the greater part of the life cycle of boro varieties is subject to cold temperature.

To determine whether the two rice groups are really distinct ecotypes in terms of thermosensitivity, 40-day-old seedlings of 80 boro and 133 aus varieties were transplanted in January 1978 in a puddled field. There were 2

seedlings/hill spaced 25 × 15 cm. The tillering potentiality in cold temperature was used as an index of thermosensitivity and measured as relative tillering rate (RTR):

$$\text{RTR} = \frac{\text{Final tiller} - \text{initial tiller number}}{\text{Initial tiller number}}$$

The RTR of all test materials was computed 30 days after transplanting